

A New Perspective on Milne-type Inequalities involving Riemann–Liouville Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

In this study, we establish the upper and below bounds for fractional Milne-type inequalities by using functions whose second derivatives are bounded. Moreover, we present new inequalities for Riemann integrals as special cases.

Keywords: Milne type inequality inequality, integral inequalities, bounded functions.

1 Introduction

The Hermite-Hadamard inequality, recognized as one of the foundational results concerning convex functions, possesses a clear geometric interpretation and has found numerous applications across various fields of mathematics. It has attracted significant attention within elementary mathematical analysis, prompting many researchers to explore generalizations, refinements, extensions, and analogous results for broader classes of functions, particularly through the lens of convexity.

The inequalities originally formulated by C. Hermite and J. Hadamard for convex functions hold a prominent place in the mathematical literature (see, for example, [12, p.137], [5]). These inequalities state that if $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function on the interval I of real numbers and $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$, then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x)dx \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Both inequalities hold in the reversed direction if f is concave.

In [7] and [8], Dragomir et al. proved the following results connected with the Hermite-Hadamard inequality:

Theorem 1.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable mapping such that there exists real constants m and M so that $m \leq f'' \leq M$. Then, the following inequalities hold:

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}. \tag{2}$$

and

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \tag{3}$$

In the following we will give some necessary definitions and mathematical preliminaries of fractional calculus theory which are used further in this paper.

Definition 1.1. Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b$$

respectively. Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

For more information about fraction calculus please refer to ([9], [10], [11], [13].)

In [14], Sarikaya et al. first give the following interesting integral inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard type involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals.

Theorem 1.2. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive function with $0 \leq a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f is a convex function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequalities for fractional integrals hold:

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b-}^\alpha f(a)] \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \tag{4}$$

with $\alpha > 0$.

Moreover, Dragomir give the following another version of Hermite-Hadamard inequality for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals:

Theorem 1.3. [6] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive function with $a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f is a convex function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequalities for fractional integrals hold:

$$\begin{aligned} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) &\leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_a^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_b^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Theorem 1.4. [1] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable function with $a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f'' is bounded, i.e. $m \leq f''(t) \leq M, t \in (a, b), m, M \in \mathbb{R}$, then we have the inequalities

$$\frac{m(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\ &\leq \frac{M(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+2)}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{m(b-a)^2}{4(\alpha+2)} \\ &\leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{M(b-a)^2}{4(\alpha+2)}, \end{aligned}$$

Now we present some Milne-type inequalities:

Theorem 1.5. [2] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable mapping (a, b) such that $f \in L_1([a, b])$. If the function $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have the following Milne-type inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5(b-a)}{24} [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|].$$

Theorem 1.6 (Milne-type inequality in the first sense). [4] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable mapping (a, b) such that $f \in L_1([a, b])$. If the function $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have the following Milne-type inequality for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{4\alpha+1}{12(\alpha+1)} (b-a) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1.7 (Milne-type inequality in the second sense). [2] Assume that the assumptions of Theorem 1.5. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha+4}{12(\alpha+1)} (b-a) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1.8 (Milne-type inequality in the third sense). [3] Assume that the assumptions of Theorem 1.5. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{b-a}{2} [\Upsilon_1(\alpha) + \Upsilon_2(\alpha)] [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$, where

$$\Upsilon_1(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1} + \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{3}, & 0 \leq \alpha \leq \frac{\ln \frac{2}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \\ \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} & \alpha > \frac{\ln \frac{2}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Upsilon_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{6}, & 0 \leq \alpha \leq \frac{\ln \frac{1}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \\ \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1} + \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{2} & \alpha > \frac{\ln \frac{1}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

2 Main Results

In this section, we will prove an upper and below bound for the difference given in Theorem 1.7 by using the functions whose second derivatives are bounded.

Theorem 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable function and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f'' is bounded, i.e. $m \leq f''(t) \leq M, t \in (a, b), m, M \in \mathbb{R}$, then we have the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b - a)^2 m & (6) \\ & \leq \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b - a)^2 M. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From the definition of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] & (7) \\ & = \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b (b - x)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx + \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (x - a)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx \right] \\ & = \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b - a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f(x) + f(a + b - x)] (x - a)^{\alpha-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Using the identity (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] & (8) \\ & \quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f(x) + f(a+b-x)] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
&= \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{3(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\begin{aligned} &4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) \\ &-3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \end{aligned} \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx.
\end{aligned}$$

Using the facts that

$$f(x) - f(a) = \int_a^x f'(t) dt$$

and

$$f(b) - f(a+b-x) = \int_{a+b-x}^b f'(t) dt,$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) && (9) \\
&= \int_{a+b-x}^b f'(t) dt - \int_a^x f'(t) dt \\
&= \int_a^x f'(a+b-u) du - \int_a^x f'(t) dt \\
&= \int_a^x [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt.
\end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have

$$f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t) dt \quad (10)$$

and

$$f(b) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f'(t) dt. \quad (11)$$

By (10) and (11), we get

$$f(a) + f(b) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f'(t)dt - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t)dt \\
 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(a+b-t)dt - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t)dt \\
 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also have

$$f'(a+b-t) - f'(t) = \int_t^{a+b-t} f''(u)du. \tag{13}$$

By using the equality (13) and $m < f''(u) < M, u \in (a, b)$, we obtain,

$$m \int_t^{a+b-t} du \leq \int_t^{a+b-t} f''(u)du \leq M \int_t^{a+b-t} du$$

i.e.

$$m(a+b-2t) \leq f'(a+b-t) - f'(t) \leq M(a+b-2t). \tag{14}$$

By integrating the inequality (14) with respect to t on $[a, x]$, from (9), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &m \left[\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)^2 \right] \\
 &\leq f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) \\
 &\leq M \left[\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)^2 \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &m(x-a)(b-x) \\
 &\leq f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) \\
 &\leq M(x-a)(b-x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Similarly, integrating the inequality (14) with respect to t on $\left[a, \frac{a+b}{2} \right]$, from (12), we obtain

$$m \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 \leq f(a) + f(b) - 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \leq M \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2. \tag{17}$$

By using the inequalities (16) and (17), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3m(x-a)(b-x) + m\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \tag{18} \\
 & \leq 4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) - 3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \\
 & \leq 3M(x-a)(b-x) + M\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying the inequality (18) by $\frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha}(x-a)^{\alpha-1}$ and integrating the resultant inequality with respect to x on $\left[a, \frac{a+b}{2}\right]$, we establish

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{m2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & \leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{3(b-a)^\alpha} \\
 & \quad \times \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - 3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & \leq \frac{M2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

By the equality (8) and equality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & = \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b-a)^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

we get the desired inequality (6).

This completes the proof. □

Remark 2.1. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{3}{8} (b-a)^2 m \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(t) dt \\
 & \leq \frac{3}{8} (b-a)^2 M.
 \end{aligned}$$

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